

PHARMACOVIGILANCE APPROACHES TO MITIGATE ADRS IN PAIN MANAGEMENT DRUGS: THE CASE OF ROFECOXIB

Juned Ali*, Nancy Badlani, Kailash Kumar

India.

Article Received on 05 Nov. 2025,
Article Revised on 25 Nov. 2025,
Article Published on 01 Dec. 2025,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17744975>

*Corresponding Author

Juned Ali

India.

How to cite this Article: Juned Ali*, Nancy Badlani, Kailash Kumar. (2025). PHARMACOVIGILANCE APPROACHES TO MITIGATE ADRS IN PAIN MANAGEMENT DRUGS: THE CASE OF ROFECOXIB. World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 14(12), 968–987.

This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

ABSTRACT

Pain management has undergone great strides with the introduction of NSAIDs and selective COX-2 inhibitors like rofecoxib, designed to relieve pain and inflammation but with minimum gastrointestinal side effects. But the case of worldwide withdrawal of rofecoxib in 2004 due to cardiovascular risks - myocardial infarction and stroke -illustrates the double-edged sword of drug innovation. This review goes into the pharmacovigilance strategies that have identified these risks, including clinical trials, post-marketing surveillance, and spontaneous reporting systems. Regulatory authorities' pivotal role in assessment and action of safety signals is illustrated in light of lessons learned from rofecoxib's case. Using its path from market launch to withdrawal, this review will illuminate a comprehensible value of effective drug safety surveillance and outline the negative ADR effects of rofecoxib so that learnings may be gleaned for future applications in the pain management

class. The rofecoxib case study forms a solid foundation for the advancement of transparency, ethical behavior, and proactive pharmacovigilance in drug development and regulation.

KEYWORDS:

1. Rofecoxib
2. COX-2 Inhibitors
3. Pharmacovigilance
4. Cardiovascular Adverse Effects

5. Post-Marketing Surveillance
6. Drug Safety Regulation

INTRODUCTION

Effective management of pain leads to improvement in the quality of life in patients with diseases such as osteoarthritis, rheumatoid arthritis, and acute pain syndromes. For almost a century, nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) have been used extensively,^[1,2] but their serious gastrointestinal side effects gave way to the development of selective COX-2 inhibitors like rofecoxib.^[3,4]

Rofecoxib (marketed under the brand name Vioxx) was marketed by Merck & Co. and approved by the FDA in 1999 as a breakthrough pain reliever, similar to an NSAID but with a superior gastrointestinal safety profile.^[5,11] It encountered serious cardiovascular risks, including myocardial infarction and stroke, during its post-marketing surveillance. It would soon lead to the withdrawal of the drug from the market across all countries in 2004-this was a defining point in the history of pharmacovigilance.^[5,6]

Figure: A VIOXX (rofecoxib) sample blister pack.

The review focuses on the efforts in pharmacovigilance, which uncovered these risks, the regulatory response, and more broadly, the implications regarding drug safety monitoring. So then, by reciting this case of rofecoxib, we intend to depict the lessons learned and proposal strategies for improvement toward safer use of pain management therapies in the future.

Drug Overview

Drug	Rofecoxib
IUPAC Name	3-(4-Methylsulfonylphenyl)-4-phenyl-2H-furan-5-one or 4-[4-(Methyl sulfonyl) phenyl]-3-phenyl-2(5H)-furanone
Brand name	Vioxx
Manufacturer	Merck & Co.
Approval Year	1999
Drug Class	COX-2-selective NSAID

Chemical Structure

Figure: Chemical structure of Rofecoxib.

Chemical and Physical Properties

S. No.	Property Name	Property Value
1.	Molecular Weight	314.4 g/mol
2.	XLogP3-AA	2.3
3.	Hydrogen Bond Donor Count	0
4.	Hydrogen Bond Acceptor Count	4
5.	Rotatable Bond Count	3
6.	Exact Mass	314.06128010 g/mol
7.	Monoisotopic Mass	314.06128010 g/mol
8.	Topological Polar Surface Area	68.8Å ²
9.	Heavy Atom Count	22
10.	Formal Charge	0
11.	Complexity	556
12.	Isotope Atom Count	0
13.	Defined Atom Stereocenter Count	0
14.	Undefined Atom Stereocenter Count	0
15.	Defined Bond Stereocenter Count	0
16.	Undefined Bond Stereocenter Count	0
17.	Covalently-Bonded Unit Count	1
18.	Compound Is Canonicalized	Yes
19.	Color / Form	White to off-white to light yellow powder
20.	Solubility	Insoluble in water. Sparingly soluble

		in acetone, slightly soluble in methanol and isopropyl acetate, very slightly soluble in ethanol, practically insoluble in octanol.
21.	Vapor Pressure	3.2X10 ⁻⁹ mm Hg at 25 °C
22.	Partition coefficient (Log)	log Kow = 1.56
23.	Henry's Law Constant	2.6X10 ⁻¹² atm-cu m/mole at 25 °C
24.	Hydroxyl radical reaction rate constant	1.3X10 ⁻¹⁰ cu cm/ molecule-sec at 25 °C

Therapeutic Uses

Rofecoxib was approved by the FDA to treat osteoarthritis, rheumatoid arthritis, juvenile rheumatoid arthritis, acute pain conditions, migraine, and dysmenorrhea.^[5]

Merck & Co., Inc. announced a voluntary withdrawal of Vioxx (rofecoxib) from the U.S. and worldwide market due to safety concerns of an increased risk of cardiovascular events (including heart attack and stroke) in patients on Vioxx. Vioxx is a prescription COX-2 selective, non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug (NSAID) that was accepted by FDA in May 1999 for the relief of the signs and symptoms of osteoarthritis, for the management of acute pain in adults, and for the treatment of menstrual symptoms, and later was accepted to treat the relief of signs and symptoms of rheumatoid arthritis in adults and children.

- **Fever**

Rofecoxib is a nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drug that selectively inhibits cyclooxygenase 2, reducing prostaglandin synthesis and offering analgesic and antipyretic activities.^[11]

- **Anti-inflammatory**

Rofecoxib is applied as an anti-inflammatory drug by being a selective inhibitor of the cyclooxygenase-2 (COX-2) enzyme, which catalyzes prostaglandins responsible for causing inflammation and pain; this selective inhibition enables rofecoxib to reduce inflammation while producing less gastrointestinal irritation compared to non-selective NSAIDs.^[7]

- **Osteoarthritis (OA)**

Osteoarthritis is the degenerative joint disease that causes pain, stiffness, and swelling, inflammation and affects a person's ability to move freely. Rofecoxib, it targets the enzyme responsible for producing inflammatory prostaglandins and reducing pain and inflammation associated with the Osteoarthritis (OA).^[8,11,13]

- **Acute Pain**

Rofecoxib is an anti-inflammatory drug that blocks COX-2 but does not interfere with the non-selective inhibition of NSAIDs; this inhibits prostaglandins that cause inflammation and pain, thus allowing rofecoxib to inhibit inflammation while being less irritating to the stomach compared to non-selective NSAIDs.^[8,11]

- **Rheumatoid Arthritis (RA)**

Rheumatoid arthritis is a chronic autoimmune disease that causes inflammation in the joints and other parts soft tissue of the body. Rofecoxib is a drug that selectively inhibits an enzyme called cyclooxygenase-2 (COX-2), which is primarily responsible for inflammation in the body, thus relieving pain in RA patients.^[11,13]

- **Primary Dysmenorrhea**

Primary dysmenorrhea is one of the main forms of pain during periods and results from natural chemicals in the uterus, which does not result from an underlying health condition.^[8,11]

- **Acute Migraine Attacks**

Rofecoxib is administrated as a medication used in the management of an acute migraine attack through its role as a COX-2 inhibitor that ensures there is reduction of inflammation as well as pain from acute migraine attacks.^[9,11]

- **Premenstrual Acne**

Premenstrual acne, or PMS acne, is one of the various forms of hormonal acne affecting many menstruating women, as hormonal balance during the menstrual cycle causes over-production of inflammatory prostaglandins in the skin that increase oil production that leads to acne. Rofecoxib is a drug that works by inhibiting the enzyme COX-2 which results in less production of inflammatory prostaglandins that lead to acne formation.^[12]

Adverse Drug Reactions (ADRs)

ADRs are unintended, harmful effects of drugs. While rofecoxib reduced GI toxicity, its selective COX-2 inhibition disrupted vascular homeostasis, leading to an increased risk of **myocardial infarction and stroke**.^[14,15,16,17,18]

Other

- **Headache,**
- **Dizziness,**
- **Somnolence,**
- **Dyspepsia,**
- **Gastrointestinal injury,**
- **Peptic ulceration,**
- **Diarrhea,**
- **Peripheral edema,**
- **Hypersensitivity reactions,**
- **Nausea,**
- **Vomiting,**
- **Hepatotoxicity.**

Pharmacodynamics

Like other NSAIDs, rofecoxib has anti-inflammatory, analgesic, and antipyretic activity. NSAIDs seem to inhibit prostaglandin synthesis through the inhibition of cyclooxygenase (COX), enzymes that catalyze the formation of prostaglandins in the arachidonic acid pathway. There are at least two isoenzymes, COX-1 and COX-2, that have been identified. Although exact mechanisms have not clearly been established, NSAIDs exert their anti-inflammatory, analgesic, and antipyretic primarily through the inhibition of COX-2. The inhibition of COX-1 is responsible for the negative effects on the GI mucosa. As rofecoxib is selective for COX-2, it may be potentially associated with a decreased risk of certain adverse events; however, further data are required to fully evaluate the drug.^[19]

Mechanism of Action (MOA)

Cyclooxygenase (COX) enzymes are part of producing prostaglandins: chemicals close to hormones that can cause pain, fever, and inflammation (11). There are two types of COX enzymes in the body: COX-1, which primarily protects the stomach, intestines, and contributes to blood clotting; and COX-2, which is mainly involved in inflammation.^[19]

FIGURE 1. Algorithm of the biochemical pathway shows that the formation of prostaglandins occurs via both cyclooxygenase enzymes (COX-1 and COX-2).

Figure.

Enzyme	Role
COX-1:	Protects the stomach and intestines, contributes to blood clotting, vasoconstriction
COX-2:	Primarily involved in inflammation (pain and swelling), vasodilator

COX-2 inhibitors are used to treat inflammatory pain. They selectively inhibit COX-2 without affecting COX-1, so the stomach and intestinal lining protection and blood clotting ability are not severely affected. COX-2 inhibitors may be beneficial in the pre- and perioperative settings.^[20]

COX inhibitors can be used to manage chronic pain conditions. Their use must be investigated in consideration of the patient's medical history, comorbidities, and medication profile. The latter must also be followed up for treatment efficacy as well as adverse effects. Rofecoxib blocks COX-2, with resultant decreased production of prostaglandin and thus inflammation and pain.^[19,21,22] It also decreases prostacyclin, a major antithrombotic molecule, with the balance thus being on the side of thrombosis.^[19,21,22,33]

Pathophysiology of ADRs

The cardiovascular ADRs stem from an imbalance between thromboxane A2 (prothrombotic) and prostacyclin (antithrombotic). This imbalance increases risks for thrombosis, myocardial infarction, and stroke during prolonged COX-2 inhibition.^[22,23,24,25]

General adverse events

General side effects have included asthenia, fatigue, dizziness, influenza-like disease, lower extremity edema, sinusitis and upper respiratory infection. Other general side effects have included abscess, chest pain, chills, contusion, cyst, diaphragmatic hernia, fever, fluid retention, flushing, fungal infection, infection, laceration, pain, pelvic pain, peripheral edema, postoperative pain, syncope, trauma, upper extremity edema, viral syndrome, cerumen impaction, epistaxis, dry throat, optic pain, otitis, otitis media, pharyngitis, tinnitus, and tonsillitis.^[5]

Figure.

• **VIGOR (Vioxx Gastrointestinal Outcomes Research) STUDY**

"VIGOR" trial stands for "Vioxx Gastrointestinal Outcomes Research" trial, referring to a clinical study that compared the gastrointestinal effects of the drug Vioxx (rofecoxib) to another nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drug (NSAID) like naproxen, primarily focusing on stomach ulcers and bleeding, but also revealing concerns about increased cardiovascular risks associated with Vioxx.^[26,27]

Figure.

Key points about the VIGOR trial

- **Drug studied:** Vioxx (rofecoxib)
 - **Main focus:** Gastrointestinal side effects like ulcers and bleeding
 - **Comparison drug:** Typically, naproxen
 - **Controversy:** The study revealed a higher rate of heart attacks in patients taking Vioxx compared to naproxen, leading to concerns about the drug's cardiovascular safety.
- **Cardiovascular Events Associated with Rofecoxib**

We report on the cardiovascular outcomes associated with the use of the selective COX-2 inhibitor rofecoxib in a long-term, multicenter, randomized, placebo-controlled, double-blind trial designed to determine the effect of three years of treatment with rofecoxib on the risk of recurrent neoplastic polyps of the large bowel in patients with a history of colorectal adenomas. [24,28,29,30]

Figure.

Methods

A total of 2586 patients with a history of colorectal adenomas underwent randomization: 1287 were assigned to receive 25 mg of rofecoxib daily, and 1299 to receive placebo. All investigator-reported serious adverse events that represented potential thrombotic cardiovascular events were adjudicated in a blinded fashion by an external committee.

RESULTS

A total of 46 patients in the rofecoxib group had a confirmed thrombotic event during 3059 patient-years of follow-up (1.50 events per 100 patient-years), as compared with 26 patients in the placebo group during 3327 patient-years of follow-up (0.78 event per 100 patient-years); the corresponding relative risk was 1.92 (95 percent confidence interval, 1.19 to 3.11;

P=0.008). The increased relative risk became apparent after 18 months of treatment; during the first 18 months, the event rates were similar in the two groups. The results primarily reflect a greater number of myocardial infarctions and ischemic cerebrovascular events in the rofecoxib group. There was earlier separation (at approximately five months) between groups in the incidence of no adjudicated investigator-reported congestive heart failure, pulmonary edema, or cardiac failure (hazard ratio for the comparison of the rofecoxib group with the placebo group, 4.61; 95 percent confidence interval, 1.50 to 18.83). Overall and cardiovascular mortality was similar in the two groups.

Outcome	Rofecoxib Group	Placebo Group
Thrombotic Events	1.50 per 100 patient-years	0.78 per 100 patient-years

CONCLUSIONS

Among patients with a history of colorectal adenomas, the use of rofecoxib was associated with an increased cardiovascular risk.^[24,28,29,30]

- **Hepatotoxicity**

Adverse hepatic effects have included borderline elevations of one or more liver tests that occurred in up to 15% of patients receiving NSAIDs. They also noted increases in ALT or AST greater than three times normal in 1% of patients during clinical trials on NSAIDs. Patients with signs and/or symptoms of liver disease or with abnormal liver tests should be closely monitored while on rofecoxib for evidence of worsening disease. If signs and symptoms consistent with liver disease develop, rofecoxib should be discontinued. Use of rofecoxib is not recommended in patients with severe hepatic insufficiency.^[5,34,35,36]

- **Renal side effects**

Renal side effects have included a decrease in glomerular filtration rate. Long-term administration of NSAIDs has resulted in renal papillary necrosis and other renal injury. Acute renal failure after a single dose of rofecoxib has been reported. Interstitial nephritis has been diagnosed in a patient 3 weeks after the start of treatment with rofecoxib.^[5,37-41]

Other

- **Nervous system**

Nervous system side effects have included headache, hypesthesia, insomnia, median nerve neuropathy, migraine, muscular spasm, paresthesia, sciatica, somnolence, and vertigo. In the

postmarketing phase of rofecoxib, aseptic meningitis has been reported to the Spontaneous Reporting System of the FDA.^[42, 44, 48]

- **Respiratory**

Respiratory side effects have included bronchitis, asthma, cough, dyspnea, pneumonia, pulmonary congestion, laryngitis, pharyngitis, allergic rhinitis, and nasal congestion.^[44, 45, 46]

- **Hematologic**

Hematologic side effects have included reports of lymphoma in less than 0.1% of patients.^[43]

- **Dermatologic**

Pseudo porphyria has been reported in a 60-year-old woman 2 weeks after the start of rofecoxib treatment for pain control. The skin lesions cleared within 1 month after discontinuation of therapy.^[48]

A 46-year-old woman who had previously developed psoriasis after exposure to a nonselective NSAID developed a severe case of psoriasis 5 days after she started taking rofecoxib for neck strain. It took several months for symptoms to abate.^[49]

PHARMACOKINETICS

- **Absorption**

The mean oral bioavailability of rofecoxib at therapeutically recommended doses of 12.5, 25, and 50 mg is approximately 93%.^[8]

- **Distribution**

At steady state, the volume of distribution as apparent for the drug is about 91 liters after giving a dose of 12.5 mg and 86 liters after a 25 mg dose. The time for peak concentration is around 2 to 3 hours. The biological half-life would be about 17 hours. Moreover, plasma protein binding is about 87%.^[8]

- **Metabolism**

Hepatic. RoBofen, is primarily metabolized through reduction by cytosolic enzymes. The major products of metabolism are the cis-dihydro and trans-dihydro derivatives of rofecoxib, which together comprise nearly 56% of recovered radioactivity in the urine. In addition, 8.8% of the dose was excreted as the glucuronide of the hydroxy derivative, a product of oxidative metabolism. Biotransformation of rofecoxib and this metabolite is reversible in humans to an

extent of less than 5%. These metabolites are inactive as inhibitors of either COX-1 or COX-2. Cytochrome P450 has a minimal role to play in metabolism of rofecoxib.^[50,54]

Figure.

• Excretion

Approximately 72% and 14% of a radioactive rofecoxib dose is eliminated in the urine as metabolites.^[8]

Alternative Pain Management Options

- **NSAIDs:** Ibuprofen, naproxen (higher GI risks).
- **Other COX-2 inhibitors:** Celecoxib (retained with monitoring).
- **Non-pharmacological:** Physiotherapy, acupuncture, turmeric supplements.

Clinical Overview

Clinical Trials

Rofecoxib was evaluated in multiple trials:

- **Early Trials:** Demonstrated effective pain relief with fewer GI side effects. (11)
- **Phase III Trials (2000):** Conducted on large populations, including the VIGOR (Vioxx Gastrointestinal Outcomes Research) study, which compared Rofecoxib to naproxen. While the study demonstrated reduced gastrointestinal bleeding, it unexpectedly revealed an increased incidence of myocardial infarctions in the Rofecoxib group.

Side Effects and ADRs

- **Common Side Effects:** Nausea, headache, dizziness.^[5]
- **Serious ADRs:** Increased risk of myocardial infarction and stroke, as highlighted in the VIGOR trial. (55)

Post-Marketing Overview

Approval and Market Introduction

- **Regulatory Authorization:** Approved by the FDA in 1999 for osteoarthritis and pain management.
- **Market Reception:** Widely embraced for its GI safety profile, generating billions in global sales.
- **Response:** Initial market reception was overwhelmingly positive. Rofecoxib generated significant revenue, with millions of prescriptions worldwide. Its perceived safety profile made it a preferred choice for pain management in elderly patients and those with a history of gastrointestinal issues.

Post-Marketing Surveillance Findings

Despite its early success, spontaneous ADR reports and observational studies revealed significant cardiovascular risks, leading to scrutiny by regulatory authorities.

Voluntary Withdrawal

- **FDA Findings**

On September 23, 2004, the FDA presented additional evidence supporting the increased risk of heart attacks among rofecoxib users.

An FDA analyst estimated that rofecoxib may have caused 88,000 to 139,000 heart attacks in five years, with 30-40% potentially fatal, though this estimate was based on a mathematical model and required cautious interpretation.

- **The Lancet Meta-Analysis (November 5, 2004)**

Concluded that rofecoxib's known cardiovascular risks warranted withdrawal years earlier.

Criticized both Merck and the FDA for allowing the drug's continued availability from 2000 to 2004.

- Ultimately, Merck voluntarily withdrew rofecoxib (Vioxx) from the global market on September 30, 2004

Role of Pharmacovigilance in Rofecoxib's Withdrawal

Detection of ADRs

Pharmacovigilance systems began receiving reports of cardiovascular events linked to Rofecoxib shortly after its widespread use.

- **Data Sources:** Data mining of spontaneous ADR reports in FDA's Adverse Event Reporting System (FAERS) identified cardiovascular signals. Reports were collected from healthcare professionals, spontaneous reporting systems, and observational studies
- **Signal Detection:** The increased frequency of myocardial infarctions and strokes among Rofecoxib users prompted PV experts to initiate investigations.

Role of Pharmacovigilance

Pharmacovigilance centers, including the WHO's Uppsala Monitoring Centre, analyzed data to assess the causality between Rofecoxib and cardiovascular events. The findings highlighted a dose-dependent increase in risk.

Reports Submitted to Regulatory Authorities

In 2004, Merck & Co. submitted detailed clinical and post-marketing data to regulatory agencies, confirming the increased cardiovascular risks associated with Rofecoxib. This report catalyzed regulatory reviews and safety assessments (FDA and EMA).

Regulatory Authority Actions

Report Review

- **Timeline:** Regulatory agencies began investigating rofecoxib's safety profile in 2001 after the VIGOR trial results and subsequent ADR reports.
- **Analysis:** The FDA reviewed epidemiological studies and mandated further investigations by Merck.

Actions Taken

- **Warnings:** In 2002, the FDA required a cardiovascular risk warning on rofecoxib's label.
- **Market Withdrawal:** Merck voluntarily withdrew rofecoxib from the global market in September 2004 after accumulating evidence of cardiovascular harm.

CONCLUSION

The saga of rofecoxib represents the promise and pitfalls of pharmaceutical innovation. As a pioneering COX-2 inhibitor, it emerged as a popular and panacea drug for pain relief with a

favorable safety profile for the gastrointestinal system. Yet, its association with serious cardiovascular events, captured in post-marketing surveillance and meta-analyses, underlines serious lacunae in pre-approval safety assessment. This underlines the importance of effective pharmacovigilance frameworks that detect and mitigate risks in real-world settings.

Rofecoxib withdrawal was the catalyst for global reforms in ADR reporting, post-marketing studies, and regulatory scrutiny that exposed the critical role of pharmacovigilance in protecting patient health. It also emphasized the responsibility of pharmaceutical companies toward transparent disclosure of safety data and decisive action when such risks arose. Therefore, real-world evidence, improved systems in ADR monitoring, and a multi-disciplinary approach for managing risk factors are what is necessary going forward. The legacy of Rofecoxib is a challenge to action: to keep patients at the center of every stage of drug development, and ensure that innovation is balanced with rigorous oversight.

DISCUSSION

Rofecoxib's case underscores the critical role of pharmacovigilance in safeguarding public health. The failure to detect cardiovascular risks during clinical trials highlights the limitations of pre-marketing studies, emphasizing the importance of robust post-marketing surveillance. Pharmacovigilance systems, through spontaneous reporting and active surveillance, successfully identified Rofecoxib's risks, leading to its withdrawal. This action averted further harm but also raised questions about the oversight of COX-2 inhibitors as a class.

Lessons from Rofecoxib

1. **Inadequate Trial Design:** Pre-market trials failed to sufficiently evaluate cardiovascular risks in broader populations.
2. **Importance of Post-Marketing Surveillance:** Pharmacovigilance systems effectively identified and escalated safety concerns.
3. **Transparency and Ethics:** Merck's delayed disclosure of adverse findings emphasized the need for ethical practices and timely reporting.

Broader Implications

Rofecoxib's case reshaped pharmacovigilance globally:

- Stricter post-marketing surveillance regulations.
- Enhanced ADR reporting systems like EudraVigilance.

- Greater emphasis on real-world evidence for drug safety.

REFERENCE

1. Center for Disease Control and Prevention. Musculoskeletal disorders. December 18, 2012. Available at: <http://www.cdc.gov/niosh/programs/msd>. Accessed, October 26, 2013.
2. James Atchison, Christopher M Herndon. "NSAIDs for Musculoskeletal Pain Management: Current Perspectives and Novel Strategies to Improve Safety" November 2013 *Journal of managed care pharmacy: JMCP*, 19(9 Supp A): 1-19 DOI:10.18553/jmcp.2013.19.s9.1 SourcePubMed
3. Foong Way David Tai A, Mark E McAlindon B, "Non-steroidal anti inflammatory drugs and the gastrointestinal tract Author information" *Clin Med (Lond)*, 2021 Mar; 21(2): 131–134. doi: 10.7861/clinmed.2021-0039 PMID: 33762373
4. Carlos Sostres MD, Carla J. Gargallo MD, Maria T. Arroyo MD, Angel Lanas MD, "Adverse effects of non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) on upper gastrointestinal tract", *April 2010; 24(2): 121-132 ELSEVIER* <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bpg.2009.11.005>
5. "Vioxx PI" (PDF). FDA. Archived (PDF) from the original on 2013-08-22. Retrieved 2019-03-27.
6. Arthur L. Weaver, MD FACP FACR. "Rofecoxib: clinical pharmacology and clinical experience," *September 2001; 23(9): 1323-1338*, [https://www.clinicaltherapeutics.com/article/S0149-2918\(01\)80112-0/abstract](https://www.clinicaltherapeutics.com/article/S0149-2918(01)80112-0/abstract)
7. O'Neil, M.J. (ed.). *The Merck Index - An Encyclopedia of Chemicals, Drugs, and Biologicals*. 13th Edition, Whitehouse Station, NJ: Merck and Co., Inc., 2001; 1481.
8. Thomson.Micromedex. *Drug Information for the Health Care Professional*. 24th ed. Volume 1. Plus Updates. Content Reviewed by the United States Pharmacopeial Convention, Inc. Greenwood Village, CO., 2004; 2495.
9. Misra UK, Jose M, Kalita J. *Postgrad Med J*. "Rofecoxib versus ibuprofen for acute treatment of migraine: a randomised placebo controlled trial," 2004 Dec; 80(950): 720-3. doi: 10.1136/pgmj.2003.012393. PMID: 15579612 Free PMC article. *Clinical Trial*.
10. Krymchantowski AV, Barbosa JS. *Cephalalgia*. "Rizatriptan combined with rofecoxib vs. rizatriptan for the acute treatment of migraine: an open label pilot study," 2002 May; 22(4): 309-12. doi: 10.1046/j.1468-2982.2002.00369.x.PMID: 12100094 *Clinical Trial*.

11. Hillson JL, Furst DE: Rofecoxib. *Expert Opin Pharmacother*, 2000 Jul; 1(5): 1053-66. [Article]
12. Tehrani R, Dharmalingam M (November 2004). "Management of premenstrual acne with Cox-2 inhibitors: a placebo controlled study". *Indian Journal of Dermatology, Venereology and Leprology*, 70(6): 345–8. PMID 17642660. Archived from the original on 2018-10-21. Retrieved 2018-10-20
13. Matheson AJ, Figgitt DP: Rofecoxib: a review of its use in the management of osteoarthritis, acute pain and rheumatoid arthritis. *Drugs*, 2001; 61(6): 833-65. [Article]
14. Bombardier, C, Laine, L, Reicin, A, et al. Comparison of upper gastrointestinal toxicity of rofecoxib and naproxen in patients with rheumatoid arthritis. *N Engl J Med.*, 2000; 343: 1520-1528.
15. Howard, PA, Delafontaine, P. Nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs and cardiovascular risk. *J Am Coll Cardiol.*, 2004; 43: 519-525
16. Solomon, DH, Glynn, RJ, Levin, R, Avorn, J. Nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drug use and acute myocardial infarction. *Arch Intern Med.*, 2002; 162: 1099-1104.
17. Solomon, DH, Schneeweiss, S, Glynn, RJ, et al. Relationship between selective cyclooxygenase-2 inhibitors and acute myocardial infarction in older adults. *Circulation.*, 2004; 109: 2068-2073.
18. Ray, WA, Stein, CM, Daugherty, JR, Hall, K, Arbogast, PG, Griffin, MR. COX-2 selective non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs and risk of serious coronary heart disease. *Lancet.*, 2002; 360: 1071-1073.
19. Chan CC, Boyce S. Rofecoxib Vioxx, MK-0966; 4-(4'-methyl-sulfonylphenyl)-3-phenyl-2-(5H)-furanone: a potent and orally active cyclooxygenase-2 inhibitor: pharmacological and biochemical profiles. *J Pharmacol Exp Ther.*, 1999; 290(2): 551–60.
20. Cashman, J.N. The Mechanisms of Action of NSAIDs in Analgesia. *Drugs*, 1996; 52(Suppl 5): 13–23. <https://doi.org/10.2165/00003495-199600525-00004>
21. Hawkey CJ. COX-1 and COX-2 inhibitors. *Best Pract Res Clin Gastroenterol*, 2001 Oct; 15(5): 801-20. doi: 10.1053/bega.2001.0236. PMID: 11566042.
22. Weir MR, Sperling RS, Reicin A, Gertz BJ. Selective COX-2 inhibition and cardiovascular effects: a review of the rofecoxib development program. *Am Heart J.*, 2003 Oct; 146(4): 591-604. doi: 10.1016/S0002-8703(03)00398-3. PMID: 14564311.
23. Bresalier RSSandler RSQuan H et al. Adenomatous Polyp Prevention on Vioxx (APPROVe) Trial Investigators, Cardiovascular events associated with rofecoxib in a

- colorectal adenoma chemoprevention trial. *N Engl J Med.*, 2005; 352(11): 1092-1102. PubMedGoogle ScholarCrossref
24. Kerr DJDunn JALangman MJ et al. VICTOR Trial Group, Rofecoxib and cardiovascular adverse events in adjuvant treatment of colorectal cancer. *N Engl J Med.*, 2007; 357(4): 360- 369. PubMedGoogle ScholarCrossref
25. van Adelsberg JGann PKo AT et al. The VIOXX in Prostate Cancer Prevention study: cardiovascular events observed in the rofecoxib 25 mg and placebo treatment groups. *Curr Med Res Opin*, 2007; 23(9): 2063- 2070. PubMedGoogle ScholarCrossref
26. Janice Hopkins Tanne, “NEJM stands by its criticism of Vioxx study” *BMJ.*, 2006 Mar 4; 332(7540): 505. doi: 10.1136/bmj.332.7540.505-a PMC
27. Bombardier, C, Laine, L, Reicin, A, et al. Comparison of upper gastrointestinal toxicity of rofecoxib and naproxen in patients with rheumatoid arthritis. *N Engl J Med.*, 2000; 343: 1520-1528.
28. Antman EMDDeMets DLoscalzo J Cyclooxygenase inhibition and cardiovascular risk. *Circulation*, 2005; 112(5): 759- 770. PubMedGoogle ScholarCrossref
29. Fitzgerald GA Coxibs and cardiovascular disease. *N Engl J Med.*, 2004; 351(17): 1709-1711. PubMedGoogle ScholarCrossref
30. Jüni PNartey LReichenbach SSterchi RDieppe PAEgger M Risk of cardiovascular events and rofecoxib: cumulative meta-analysis. *Lancet*, 2004; 364(9450): 2021-2029. PubMedGoogle ScholarCrossref
31. Bresalier RSSandler RSQuan H et al. Adenomatous Polyp Prevention on Vioxx (APPROVe) Trial Investigators, Cardiovascular events associated with rofecoxib in a colorectal adenoma chemoprevention trial. *N Engl J Med.*, 2005; 352(11): 1092-1102. PubMedGoogle ScholarCrossref
32. van Adelsberg JGann PKo AT et al. The VIOXX in Prostate Cancer Prevention study: cardiovascular events observed in the rofecoxib 25 mg and placebo treatment groups. *Curr Med Res Opin.*, 2007; 23(9): 2063- 2070. PubMedGoogle ScholarCrossref
33. Thomson.Micromedex. Drug Information for the Health Care Professional. 24th ed. Volume 1. Plus Updates. Content Reviewed by the United States Pharmacopeial Convention, Inc. Greenwood Village, CO., 2004; 2495.
34. Papachristou GI, Demetris AJ, Rabinovitz M. Acute cholestatic hepatitis associated with long-term use of rofecoxib. *Dig Dis Sci.*, 2004; 49: 459–61. [PubMed]

35. Haider M, Gain E, Khadem G, Pilmore H, Yun K, Jayasinghe N, Walker R. Simultaneous presentation of rofecoxib-induced acute hepatitis and acute interstitial nephritis. *Intern Med J.*, 2005; 35: 370–2. [PubMed]
36. Yan B, Leung Y, Urbanski SJ, Myers RP. Rofecoxib-induced hepatotoxicity: a forgotten complication of the coxibs. *Can J Gastroenterol.*, 2006; 20: 351–5. [PMC free article] [PubMed]
37. Perazella MA, Eras J (2000) "Are selective COX-2 inhibitors nephrotoxic?." *Am J Kidney Dis.*, 35; 937-40.
38. Swan SK, Rudy DW, Lasseter KC, et al. (2000) "Effect of cyclooxygenase-2 inhibition on renal function in elderly persons receiving a low-salt diet." *Ann Intern Med.*, 133: 1-9.
39. Ofran Y, Bursztyn M, Ackerman Z (2001) "Rofecoxib-induced renal dysfunction in a patient with compensated cirrhosis and heart failure." *Am J Gastroenterol*, 96: 1941.
40. Alim N, Peterson L, Zimmerman SW, Updike S (2003) "Rofecoxib-induced acute interstitial nephritis." *Am J Kidney Dis.*, 41: 720-1.
41. Reinhold SW, Fischereeder M, Riegger GA, Kramer BK (2003) "Acute renal failure after administration of a single dose of a highly selective COX-2 inhibitor." *Clin Nephrol*, 60: 295-6.
42. Daugherty KK, Gora-Harper ML (2002) "Idiopathic paresthesia reaction associated with rofecoxib." *Ann Pharmacother*, 36: 264-6.
43. Meyer C, Gahler R (2002) "Central retinal vein occlusion in a patient with rheumatoid arthritis taking rofecoxib." *Lancet*, 360: 1100.
44. Ehrich EW, Schnitzer TJ, McIlwain H, Levy R, Wolfe F, Weisman M, Zeng Q, Morrison B, Bolognese J, Seidenberg B, Gertz BJ (1999) "Effect of specific COX-2 inhibition in osteoarthritis of the knee: A 6 week double blind, placebo controlled pilot study of rofecoxib." *J Rheumatol*, 26: 2438-47.
45. Cannon GW, Caldwell JR, Holt P, McLean B, Seidenberg B, Bolognese J, Ehrich E, Mukhopadhyay S, Daniels B (2000) "Rofecoxib, a specific inhibitor of cyclooxygenase 2, with clinical efficacy comparable with that of diclofenac sodium - Results of a one-year, randomized, clinical trial in patients with osteoarthritis of the knee and hip." *Arthritis Rheum*, 43: 978-87.
46. Crofford LJ (2003) "COX-2: Where are we in 2003? - Specific cyclooxygenase-2 inhibitors and aspirin-exacerbated respiratory disease." *Arthritis Res Ther.*, 5: 25-7.
47. Bonnel RA, Villalba ML, Karwoski CB, Beitz J (2002) "Aseptic meningitis associated with rofecoxib." *Arch Intern Med.*, 162: 713-5.

48. Markus R, Reddick ME, Rubenstein MC (2004) "Rofecoxib-induced pseudoporphyria." *J Am Acad Dermatol*, 50.
49. Clark DW, Coulter DM (2003) "Psoriasis associated with rofecoxib." *Arch Dermatol*, 139: 1223.
50. Papachristou GI, Demetris AJ, Rabinovitz M. Acute cholestatic hepatitis associated with long-term use of rofecoxib. *Dig Dis Sci.*, 2004; 49: 459–61. [PubMed]
51. Haider M, Gain E, Khadem G, Pilmore H, Yun K, Jayasinghe N, Walker R. Simultaneous presentation of rofecoxib-induced acute hepatitis and acute interstitial nephritis. *Intern Med J.*, 2005; 35: 370–2. [PubMed]
52. Yan B, Leung Y, Urbanski SJ, Myers RP. Rofecoxib-induced hepatotoxicity: a forgotten complication of the coxibs. *Can J Gastroenterol.*, 2006; 20: 351–5. [PMC free article] [PubMed]
53. Halpin RA, Porras AG, Geer LA, et al. The disposition and metabolism of rofecoxib, a potent and selective cyclooxygenase-2 inhibitor, in human subjects. *Drug Metab Dispos.*, 2002; 30: 684–93
54. Rita A. Halpin, Arturo G. Porras, Leslie A. Geer, Margaret R. Davis, Donghui Cui, George A. Doss, Eric Woolf, Donald Musson, Catherine Matthews, Ralph Mazenko, Jules I. Schwartz, Kenneth C. Lasseter, Kamlesh P. Vyas and Thomas A. Baillie The Disposition and Metabolism of Rofecoxib, a Potent and Selective Cyclooxygenase-2 Inhibitor, in Human Subjects, *Drug Metabolism and Disposition* June, 2002; 30(6): 684-693. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1124/dmd.30.6.684>
55. Baron JA, Sandler RS, Bresalier RS, Lanas A, Morton DG, Riddell R, Iverson ER, Demets DL: Cardiovascular events associated with rofecoxib: final analysis of the APPROVe trial. *Lancet*. 2008 Nov 15; 372(9651): 1756-64. doi: 10.1016/S0140-6736(08)61490-7. Epub 2008 Oct 14. [Article]